

Studies on the Absorption Spectra of Phenol Betaines Containing Benzimidazole Nucleus. Part III

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A series of phenol betaines derived from hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazole and their nitro derivatives has been synthesised. Their absorption spectra have been studied. They show a characteristic charge-transfer absorption band in the visible region which is not shown by the parent conjugate acid in ethanol. This characteristic absorption band undergoes a blue shift (in the longer wavelength) in the hydroxylic solvents which is attributed to hydrogen bonding. The shift of this characteristic band in polar solvents is in keeping with the nature of charge-transfer absorption band and is in conformity with the dipolar nature of these betaines.

THIS paper is in continuation of our work on phenol betaines^{1,2}. In our previous communication, synthesis and the absorption spectra of phenol betaines derived from hydroxy-4-stilbazole³ and hydroxystyryl-2-quinoline⁴ have been described.

This paper deals with the synthesis and the absorption spectra of phenol betaines derived from hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazole and their nitro-derivatives. Only the betaines I, II and III were found to be stable, apparently due to their existence in the non-polar quinone form. No stable betaines could be isolated from the methiodides of phenols containing OH in the meta position of 2 and 4 despite the fact that they gave deep colour with dilute alkali. The instability of these betaines is attributed to their inability to exist in the non-polar quinonoid structures as in I, II and III which were stable and could be isolated.

These betaines have been identified by preparing their picrates. The absorption spectra have been recorded in Tables 2 and 3. In case of those

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF THE VARIOUS BETAINES

Sl. No.	Compound	Absorption maxima					
		Ethanol		Chloroform		Benzene	
		λ_{max} nm	log ϵ	λ_{max} nm	log ϵ	λ_{max} nm	log ϵ
1.	Betaine I	265	3.92	260	4.93	347	3.75
		350	4.36	944	4.34	525	2.62
				520	2.44		
2.	Betaine II	350	4.29	—	—	—	—
3.	Betaine III	285	4.05	285	4.24	254	4.75
		345	4.05	350	4.27	522	3.47
				530	3.53		

(Containing 10% ethanol) (Containing 10% ethanol)

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF THE METHIODIDES

The quaternary iodide of Sl. No.	Acidic Ethanol		Alkaline Ethanol	
	λ_{max} nm	log ϵ	λ_{max} nm	log ϵ
1.	270	4.01	320	4.33
	325	4.31	395	3.66
	367	4.39	400	4.17
2.	248	3.99	—	—
	337	4.45	365	4.85
3.	269	3.92	318	4.36
	371	4.56	395-400	4.35
4.	300	4.29	317	4.40
	355	4.49	370-375	4.38
5.	251	4.15	—	—
	382	4.59	400	4.40

methiodides from which stable betaines could not be isolated, the absorption spectra of parent quaternary methiodides were recorded at different pH, which showed absorption at longer wavelengths in alkaline medium. By this method the absorption maxima of the unstable betaines could also be studied.

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	Compound	Time of reflux	Colour	Recrystallization Solvent	M.P. (°C)	Analysis%
1.	2'-hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazole (C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂)	12 hours	yellow	aq. ethanol	250-51	Found: C, 76.6; H, 4.7; N, 11.3; Reqd. C, 76.2; H, 5.0; N, 11.8
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ON ₂ I)	2 hours	yellow	acetone	215	Found: I, 31.9; Reqd. I, 32.3
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂)	—	yellow	ethanol	207	Found: N, 15.8; Reqd. N, 16.2
	Betaine I	—	dark-red	—	158	M.P. of the picrate 207°
2.	3'-hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazole (C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂)	12 hours	yellow	aq. ethanol	207	Found: C, 76.6; H, 4.8; N, 11.4; Reqd. C, 76.2; H, 5.08; N, 11.8
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ON ₂ I)	2½ hours	yellow	acetone	249-51	Found: I, 31.89; Reqd. I, 32.9
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₂)	—	yellow	ethanol	202	Found: N, 15.8; Reqd. N, 16.2
	Betaine II	—	dark-red	—	198	M.P. of the picrate 217°
3.	2-(2'-hydroxystyryl)-5(6)-nitrobenzimidazole (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃)	10 hours	yellow	aq. acetone	282-83	Found: C, 63.5; H, 3.69; N, 18.9; Reqd. C, 63.8; H, 3.91; N, 18.5
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ I)	2 hours	yellow	acetone	251-54	Found: I, 28.72; Reqd. I, 29.0
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃)	—	yellow	ethanol	218	Found: N, 15.1; Reqd. N, 15.4
	Betaine III	—	dark-red	—	198	M.P. of the picrate 217°
4.	2-(3'-hydroxystyryl)-5(6)-nitrobenzimidazole (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃)	12 hours	yellow	aq. ethanol	292	Found: C, 64.4; H, 3.65; N, 18.1; Reqd. C, 64.0; H, 3.9; N, 18.5
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ I)	2½ hours	yellow	acetone	244-46	Found: I, 28.8; Reqd. I, 29.0
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃)	—	yellow	ethanol	273 (decomp.)	Found: N, 15.0; Reqd. N, 15.6
	Betaine III	—	dark-red	—	184 (first sweels) 160 (volume double)	M.P. of the picrate 244
5.	2-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxystyryl)-5(6)-nitrobenzimidazole (C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃)	5 hours	yellow	aq. ethanol	207	Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.39; N, 12.8; Reqd. C, 61.7; H, 4.18; N, 13.1
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ I)	3 hours	yellow	acetone	264	Found: I, 26.6; Reqd. I, 27.1
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₃)	—	yellow	ethanol	244	Found: N, 13.5; Reqd. N, 14.1
	Betaine III	—	dark-red	—	184 (first sweels) 160 (volume double)	M.P. of the picrate 244

Experimental

All melting points have been determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. UV absorption Spectra were recorded on a Beckman Spectrophotometer, Model DU-2, using 1 cm path length quartz cells.

Preparation of hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazoles—0.02 mol of the appropriate hydroxybenzaldehyde viz., salicylaldehyde, *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin was boiled under reflux with 0.02 mol of 2 methyl benzimidazole/2 methyl-5(6)-nitrobenzimidazole⁵ in the presence of 2 ml of acetic anhydride, on an oil bath at 160-170° for a period ranging from 5 to 12 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled. The solid separated was filtered and washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted hydroxybenzaldehyde. The product was recrystallised from appropriate solvent.

Preparation of methiodides of hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazoles—The required amount of the hydroxystyryl-2-benzimidazole was dissolved in 1:1 ethanol-acetone solution and was heated under reflux with excess of methyl iodide for 1 to 2 hrs., when the desired methiodide separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from acetone.

Preparation of the phenol betaines—The desired methiodide was dissolved in absolute alcohol and the solution was warmed with excess of silver carbonate suspended in the solution. When an intense yellow coloured solution of the betaine in ethanol was obtained. The solution was filtered and ethanol was removed under reduced pressure giving a yellow or dark red solid.

The melting points and analyses of the various compounds prepared are given in Table 3.

Discussion

A study of the absorption maxima of betaines^{1,2} shows the appearance of a characteristic internal charge-transfer absorption band in the visible region. This band is bathochromically shifted in the chloroform and benzene due to dipolar interaction, whereas in ethanol it appears at a lower wavelength which is attributed to hydrogen bond.

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